

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

Grant agreement number: 101082057

DELIVERABLE D7.13 EU Clustering Activities 2

Lead party for deliverable: Wageningen University

Document type: R

Due date of deliverable: 31-07-2024

Actual submission date: 05-08-2024

Version: 1.0

Dissemination level: Public

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WP	Task	Deliverable	Authors (lead and others)	Participant organisation	Dissemination level	Report Date & Version	Deliverable Delivery date (month)
7	7.13	D36	Verina Ingram	WU	PU	VI 05082024	31-07-2024

Partners

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Suggested citation: Verina Ingram (2024) EU Clustering Activities 2. Deliverable D36 V1.0 Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands

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This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.

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TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrofood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agro-food trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrofood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities to enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations

TCforBE aims and objectives

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrofood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and on how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agro-food trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026), will support **transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrofood systems**. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation.

The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

Box 1: TCforBE Specific Objectives

Objective 1: Deepen understanding and capacity of agrofood policymakers on transformative pathways for biodiversity and equity in EU telecoupled agrofood systems.

Objective 2: Identify, assess, and engage EU policymakers and stakeholders on demand-side consumer country governance arrangements for transformative change in telecoupled EU agrofood systems for positive biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Objective 3: Analyse and assess the potentials and limitations of existing biodiversity metrics, measurements, and finance levers (EU Action 68) and derive innovative financial instruments to achieve high biodiversity business transformations that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics (EU Actions 72 and 73).

Objective 4: Identify, co-analyse, and assess, with policymakers and stakeholders, national supply side producer country policies, scenarios and transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

Objective 5: To co-generate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes, with high biodiversity and equity outcomes, drawing on new evidence and tools on biodiversity imaginaries, commodity impacts, SLI effectiveness/impacts, and corporate/regenerative enterprise.

Objective 6: Synthesise evidence and build global, regional and landscape learning to foster transformative change on biodiversity and equity.

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.
- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.
- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP 4 – national scale engagement and research – identification of current visions of future relating to food and territories (Q methodology), followed by social processes and researcher led activities to co-frame and co-learn on transformative change pathways including generation of scenarios, geospatial mapping of commodity and policy impacts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 will involve a conceptual framing, but also synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape and global / EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.
- WP7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agro-food system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

Figure 1.

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low and middle income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales (see Table 1) through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale (see three landscapes* in Table 1): participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.

Table 1 The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics & telecoupled agri-food commodities
Cameroon	*Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High biodiversity forested landscape with conservation area: Dja Biosphere Reserve, with indigenous ethnic groups • Increasing trade in cocoa, timber, non-timber forest products (NTFP), oil palm (national & local trade) • Encroachment, fragmentation, and degradation of Dja Biosphere Reserve, restrictions to customary use by Baka ethnic groups, illegal logging, ivory and bushmeat hunting, increased infrastructure, mining and agro-plantations (rubber, oil palm) • Conservation & Sustainable landscape initiatives: Dja Green cocoa landscape and Roadmap to deforestation free cocoa; REDD in Southern humid forested plateau (ERP1); Forum of Dja Actors; Synergy Platform between Ngoyla-Mintom Actors (SYAMINGO); Technical Operational Units (TOUs); Model Forests. • Medium-high levels of telecoupling cocoa to EU
Colombia	LLanos Orientales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Megadiverse landscape 20% protected areas, 30% communal lands, reforestation programs • Agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, national and export trade. • Violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence, appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders • Conservation & Sustainable landscape initiatives: Colombia-Orinoquia Integrated Sustainable Landscape Initiative Green cocoa landscape • Medium-high levels of telecoupling palm oil, banana and coffee to EU
	*Magdalena Department, Santa Marta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High biodiversity from sea, dry tropical forest remnants to Sierra Nevada foothills • Long history agricultural expansion for banana, cocoa and oil palm export trade • Violence, illicit economies, labour equity and working conditions, and weak state presence. • Conservation projects & Sustainable landscape initiatives: Cesar, Huila and Magdalena, Colombia PPI compacts with IDH; SAN, ISEAL & Swiss State Secretariat Blueprint for Sustainable landscape • High levels of telecoupling of cocoa, palm oil, banana and coffee to EU
Kenya	*Mau forest – Masai-Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High biodiversity forests, savannah and wetlands with protected and conservation areas, important water catchment area with indigenous ethnic groups, community forests and water users associations • Expanding rice and fish farming lower Yala and Nyando Basins, grasslands with grazing systems, highlands tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP, horticulture local, national and export trade • Conservation & Sustainable landscape initiatives : Regenerative, conservation & SLIs: MaMaSe program • Medium levels of telecoupling of tea, avocado, horticulture products to EU
	Mt Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High biodiversity forests with conservation area: Mt Kenya National Park, Masai Mara National Reserve with indigenous ethnic groups • Grasslands (grazing systems) and coffee- tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems, national and export trade • Large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas & extensive agriculture • Conservation & Sustainable landscape initiatives: Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration • Medium-high levels of telecoupling tea, avocado, horticulture products to EU

Introduction

This second report on Clustering Activities is the result of a collaborative effort among the 11 projects in the cluster (see Appendix 1) funded under the EU Horizon Europe Transformative Change for Biodiversity call (HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01) and other EU Horizon 2020 projects (see Appendix 2). The projects in this cluster all aim at fostering cooperation, knowledge sharing, and effective communication between the participating projects to achieve better results collectively.

Within the Cluster the following projects have synergies and complementarities: TC4BE, CLEVER, BIOTRAILS, BAMBOO, BIOTRAILS, BioValue and RAINFOREST (see Appendix 1) and other Horizon 2020 projects such as FOSTA Health (see Appendix 2). Through similar aims, methods, themes, cases research methods, focus countries and advisory boards, TC4BE is more closely associated with these projects. BAMBOO is also initiator of a Horizon Results Booster project group which includes RAINFOREST, CLEVER and BIOTRAILS. TRANSPATH has a budget of 45k for workshops/dialogues and communications as a Cluster of EU Horizon projects.

The specific objective of Clustering activities is to identify common arenas for the projects, identify potential synergies that can be achieved by working together, and boost results through joint efforts.

The first Cluster plan (Deliverable D7.12 D35 from December 2022 to May 2023) and subsequent activities were developed following on meetings with other EU project representatives online and one on one project meetings. Our clustering activities have been shared and documents uploaded to a [Clustering Action Plan - Dropbox](#).

The outcomes are activities are taken jointly, in smaller groups and bilaterally. While not all of the measures outlined in the Clustering Activities Plan will be taken by all projects, each project has agreed to collaborate on one or more measures. The measures which TC4BE proposes are shown below.

Clustering Activities Plan

Network-Related Activities

These include putting each other on each other's websites, inviting each other to annual/final events, sharing publications, and following each other on social media. These activities will help increase the visibility and recognition of each project's work, creating a stronger sense of collaboration and promoting the exchange of ideas.

TC4BE Network-Related activities include:

- Creating a shared list of communication representatives of each project so that the projects can easily share communication outputs with each other. The list is shared for all interested projects and anyone can send emails to the list.
- Putting other Cluster project links on TC4BE website
- Inviting each other to annual/final events
- Sharing publications
- Following other projects on social media

Content-Related Activities

This includes collaboration on a small set of deliverables where common interests exist and data sharing. By collaborating on a small set of deliverables, the projects can ensure that their work complements and enhances the work of the others, thereby maximizing the collective impact. Data sharing will enable each project to build on the findings of the others, leading to more comprehensive and robust results.

TC4BE Content-Related activities include:

- Participation in the Values, norms and justice Working Group (led by TRANSPATH, Jeanne Nel and Sebastian Kaye), with agreed actions in the next 6 months:

- Virtual meeting within the first 3 months of the working group
 - Earth Systems Governance Conference, 24-26 October
 - 1-pager template on dealing with social justice
 - Development of an action plan for this working group to agree on shared activities.
- Exchanges during SCORAI-ERSCP-WUR 'Transforming Consumption-Production Systems toward just and sustainable futures' conference June 2023, Wageningen University.
 - Exchanges during 2023 Radboud Earth System conference October 2023
 - Collaboration on a set of deliverables where common interests exist and for efficient data sharing:
 - Cocoa value chain - TRANSPATH
 - Project work in Cameroon – with CLEVER
 - Theory and pathways of Transformative change with BIOTraCes
 - Link modelling work (explore assumptions and outcomes) with BIOTRAILS

Results Boosting Activities

This includes the possibility of actively participating in at least two final events. Projects with the same timeline deadline, as well as projects that have one-year ending year differences, have agreed to organize two joint events in 2025 and 2026. In this respect, the possibility of organizing the final conferences in Brussels with invited keynote speakers is being considered. The second activity included here is considering the development of a short document that delivers joint results and their implications for some of the projects. These activities will help boost the results of the projects and increase the impact of their findings.

TC4BE Results Boosting activities include:

- Intention to participate in one or both final project boosting activities

Monitoring Activities

In order to ensure that collaboration activities continue and corrections are made when necessary, all projects involved have decided to meet every six months to discuss progress and collaboration, and to discuss what facilitated and what hindered the collaboration. The success criteria will be based on the success of projects in involving activities in each theme of collaboration. All projects have agreed to follow several network-related activities. However, in smaller groups, they will also focus on some content and dissemination-related activities. Although all projects will involve monitoring activities every six months to ensure the success of the collaboration, they will also have specific monitoring activities tailored to their individual collaborations.

TC4BE Monitoring activities include:

- Participate in 6 monthly cluster meetings

Cluster & other EU Horizon project contact persons

Project	Contact point	
	Name	Email
TC4BE	Verina Ingram	verina.ingram@wur.nl
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FoSTA Health	Stephen Whitfield	S.Whitfield@leeds.ac.uk
BAMBOO	Francesca Verones	francesca.verones@ntnu.no
BioValue	Rute Martins Maria Partidário	mariapartidario@tecnico.ulisboa.pt rutemartins@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
BIONEXT	Maija Airos	Maija.Airos@syke.fi
TRANSPATH	Jeanne Nel	jeanne.nel@wur.nl
BIOTRAILS	Raffaele Giordano Evangelia Drakou	raffaele.giordano@cnr.it e.drakou@hua.gr
BIOTraCes	Jeanne Nel Roel During	jeanne.nel@wur.nl roel.during@wur.nl

Synergies and collaboration with CLEVER

Following on from meeting in Brussels, online 03 May 2023, 05 June 2023, 23 November and 28 November 2023 where the following synergies and areas of collaboration were agreed:

1. TC4BE focuses on agricultural **commodities**, while CLEVER focuses on timber. In terms of policy/governance research, both projects cover Cameroon: TC4BE more from a territorial governance point of view, CLEVER from a value chain governance point of view.
2. As part of TC4BE, UDS conducts a **rapid analysis of policies** and measures around biodiversity governance and a stakeholder analysis on national and landscape levels in Cameroon. Under CLEVER, EFI and UDS examine Cameroon domestic policies & regulations (e.g., what outcomes do they intend to achieve?) and conduct a mapping of timber value chain actors. These activities can be synergistic.
3. On the consumer (EU) side, TC4BE focuses on the Netherlands, the UK, and France, where consumer surveys are envisaged through partners. CLEVER does not target **consumers as such but goes down to the level of retailers in the value chain**. In this area, collaboration can be explored down the road with Marina Benitez Kanter (Wageningen PhD on TC4BE) the contact person..
4. TC4BE partners do **Bayesian modelling** on agricultural commodities on a landscape level in Cameroon (University of Greenwich) and trade flow analysis at a regional scale in Africa (CIRAD). CLEVER (UPV & IIASA) develops modelling options to model biodiversity impacts of different policy options and supply chain initiatives, and based on that models biodiversity impacts of trade. The corresponding experts from each project could explore potential for synergies. Verina to check with TC4BE partners if they see potential for and interest in collaboration with CLEVER, e.g., WPs 6&7 focused on modelling.
5. **Cross-review** of each other's relevant draft Deliverables; could be helpful for example due to different, complementary perspectives (e.g., modelling) in the two projects.
6. As projects progress, we continue to explore possibilities for **joint outputs** (e.g., scientific articles, policy briefs) can be explored.
7. **Further exchanges** on collaboration between TC4BE and CLEVER to be held in the form of meetings (roughly bi-annually and on an ad-hoc basis) and with email communication. A next online meeting to be held after the summer break, before EFI goes to Cameroon for data collection tentatively in late September 2023. Mathias to send a meeting invite.
8. **Exchange of online data collection in Cameroon**, Discussed and shared our proposed **pathways of influence and stakeholders** in our project theories of change at CLEVER's annual meeting 28 November 2023 and during fieldwork in October-November 2023.
9. **Shared our WP6 social learning methodology**.

Synergies and collaboration with TRANSPATH

Following on from meeting in Brussels and online 03 May 2023, and several in person meetings in Wageningen the following synergies and areas of collaboration were discussed:

1. Cocoa and other **agrifood commodity value chain** links: CLEVER, TRANSPATH, TC4BE are all working on telecoupled cocoa, but in different countries. TC4BE works in Cameroon and TRANSPATH in Ghana. BIONEXT, BIOVALUE, RAINFOREST, SUSTAIN also have interesting links on this subject.
2. **Conceptual frameworks**: Our conceptual frameworks overlap in content and we have shared slides from the ESG and SOCRAI conferences (Ingram et al. 2023a, Ingram et al. 2023b) conferences to aid our reflections on similarities, differences and framings. Where we have good complementarity is in the focus of where we are looking for leverage points (TRANSPATH emphasise change agents in financial and trade; whereas TC4BE emphasis landscape and national levels).
3. **Joint review of Deliverables**:
 - TRANSPATH PhD Paul Dingkuhn is mapping out global cocoa initiatives and Verina can review this. Verina gave an overview of current cocoa initiatives in 2018. <https://www.mdpi.com/books/pdfdownload/book/1248#page=208>. Action: Jeanne to introduce Paul and Verina; Verina to introduce Paul to the Finland team.
 - TC4BE: busy with a conceptual review of leverage points and levers in a conceptual review. Then also looking at a policy review. For both, we could think about reviewing

work. There are different moments to review this, e.g. SCB conference in July 23; ESG conference in October 23. Verina send out details of these events.

- Online workshop after review to look at similarities and contrasts. Objective is not so much to align, but to learn from the diversity of framings and approaches.
- TRANSPATH deliverables in next 12 months interesting for review/collaboration are:
 - D1.1 (conceptual framework for the emergence of positive tipping points – includes leverage points, policy mixes and other interventions)
 - D1.2 (downscaling the safe and just operating space)
 - D2.1 (roadmap for setting up science-policy-practitioner labs)
 - D4.2 review of policy interventions and entry points in trade regulations, financial sector and international commodity value chains.

TC4BE deliverables interesting for review/collaboration are:

- D0* Conceptual paper
 - D2.3 Transformative change consumer pathways report
 - D3.1 Report on the finance instruments and related regulations
 - D4.1 Drivers/commodity impacts on biodiversity report
 - D4.3 Report on co-generated transformative change pathways for biodiversity-rich LMICs for biodiversity and equity
 - D6.1 Report on synthesis of evidence and lessons learned
 - D6.2 Report on outcomes of global dialogues
4. **Earth systems Governance conference October 2023:** Jeanne organized a parallel event (Nel et al. 2023) to get together the cluster project team members as knowledge sharing.
 5. **Further exchanges** will follow between TC4BE and TRANSPATH.

Synergies and collaboration with BIOTraCES

Following on from the kick-off cluster meeting in Brussels and meetings in Wageningen the following areas of collaboration were conducted:

1. Shared BIOTraCes **Theory of change** & TCforBEs conceptual framework
2. **Further exchanges** will continue between TC4BE and BIOTraCes.
3. Reviewed **D1.1 Theory of Change** as part of our WP2 theory of change and conceptual paper (Nelson et al. 2024)
4. Shared **our progress and slides** at BIOTRAILS WEBINAR in May 2024

Synergies and collaboration with RAINFOREST

Verina Ingram (TC4BE project coordinator) was invited to be an advisory board member on the RAINFOREST project. This brings a good complementarity with TC4BE's work as RAINFOREST aims to identify and give recommendations for the most efficient transformative pathways and leverage points to halt and reverse biodiversity loss. The scientific advisory board of 3-5 key scientists for regular engagements throughout the project. These engagements would take place once or twice a year during the consortia meetings, with the aim of garnering feedback and input on our narratives, models and scientific results. Verina's expertise has been identified as important to our research, in addition to the relationship to a project in the same cluster.

1. Participated in **Rainforest's D1.1 AND 5.1 Scenarios sessions** in their annual project meeting 4-5 October 2023

Synergies and collaboration with FOSTA

An online meeting with the project coordinator at University of Leeds has taken place to share ideas and experiences on inclusive and participatory modelling (e.g., how to include critical social approaches in modelling), and learning from internal project reflection. It was agreed to continue the discussion and learning from each other, through meetings or joining research group presentations. There may be potential to write together on learnings on working with critical social approaches in modelling.

Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations Biodiversity Cluster Working Group 3

Following on from the Brussels meeting in March, a Working group has been set up, coordinated by Jeanne Nel Jeanne.nel@wur.nl (BIOTRACES, TRANSPATH) and Sebastien Kaye sebastien.kaye@unep-wcmc.org. Members of the group are BIOTRAILS, SUSTAIN, TRANSPATH, PLANET4B, TC4BE and BIOVALUE. We had an online meeting 29 June 2024

Main points of discussion

Original framing: “Beyond GDP: fostering intangible values and valuation of nature. Intersectionality, Behaviours, Gender, Beliefs and Community knowledge for biodiversity policy-making”:

- Beyond GDP does not conflict with our goals but we have a broader focus
- Policy making vs ability of people to make pro-biodiversity decisions. The Working Group goes beyond just policy. It is also about how individuals make decisions in every day life. However, to acknowledge that policy has a prime role to power agency, and to bring in the democratic and justice lens at a systemic level. We need to bring in the democratization of decision-making processes, and also emphasize that it is not just institutions and policy, but also society.
- Transforming research: Knowledge is not only from researchers, but can be a plurality of different ways of knowing. So it is also about the characterization of research itself to transform.
- Plural values of nature vs valuation of nature: plural values encompasses all. The original context intended to emphasize that we need to move towards acknowledging intangible values and account for externalities. But now we want to move beyond the ‘beyond GDP’

Collaborations

BIOTRAILS workshop to capture the plural values related to the norms and behaviours in cocoa value chains. Will invite other projects working on cocoa value chain, including: CLEVER, TC4BE and TRANSPATH. Contact: Evangelia Drakou e.drakou@hua.gr

SUSTAIN and TRANSPATH to link up to talk about approaches to mapping biodiversity impacts and dependencies in business chains. Contacts: Martin Lok and Jeanne Nel Jeanne.nel@wur.nl

PLANET4B are mapping related projects and synergies (synergy strategy), which has an associated database of projects. This could be broadened into some mapping across the Cluster of Transformative projects if there is a shared need. Contacts: Ilkhom Soliev ilkhom.soliev@zirs.uni-halle.de

Workshop on diverse conceptualizations of transformative change: TC4BE, BIOTRACES, TRANSPATH will be running a session on this and we could connect others in the Cluster. BIOVALUE would like to be connected to this. Contacts: Thirze Hermans thirze.hermans@wur.nl

A shared calendar of events would be handy. TC4BE, TRANSPATH, BIOTRACES, PLANET4B have all submitted proposals for special sessions at the Earth System Governance Conference, Netherlands, 24-26 October 2023. We could use this as a common next meeting point, and a chance to engage more broadly with the research community around transformative change and biodiversity. Contacts: Jeanne Nel Jeanne.nel@wur.nl, Sebastien Kaye sebastien.kaye@unep-wcmc.org and Thirze Hermans thirze.hermans@wur.nl

We aim to communicate how each of our projects are dealing with social justice. To use this as a starting point of discussion for transformative projects. Including intergenerational justice, to make this much more explicit. For example: working with schools and youth; using approaches like discount rates works against intergenerational justice. PLANET4B and BIOTRACES both work with schools. When it comes to justice and intersectionality it is about how decision making affects identity. Contact: Robin Dianoux robin.dianoux@inrae.fr

EU cluster joint activities May 2023-July 2024

1. **Virtual meetings** within to continue exchanges and identify shared synergies between projects to inform the creation of a joint working plan to maximise collaboration between Horizon

Europe projects in this working group. Contact: Sebastien Kaye sebastien.kaye@unep-wcmc.org.

2. After the April 2023 and a second meeting up in June 2023, in which an action plan of cross cluster activities was made, we had a meeting on 06 March 2024.
3. **Earth Systems Governance (ESG) Conference, 24-26 October.** We participated in sessions led by TC4BE (Ingram et al. 2023a, Ingram et al. 2023b), BIOTRACES/TRANSPATH, PLANET4B), organized a side meeting and supper. Actions: Jeanne Nel, Thirze Hermans, Ilkhom Soliev and Sebastien Kaye. Contacts: Jeanne Nel Jeanne.nel@wur.nl, Sebastien Kaye sebastien.kaye@unep-wcmc.org and Thirze Hermans thirze.hermans@wur.nl.
4. Each project in the Working Group completed a **1-pager template on they deal with social justice**. Actions: Robin Dianoux will develop the 1-page template.
5. **Communication network meeting** online led by Maija Auirlos FEI BIONEXT on 7 June 2024 and meeting on 20 June 2024 during which developed a [National level dissemination plan](#) together.

Upcoming activities

1. Joint sessions proposed by other EU Cluster members accepted as part of **Wageningen Centre for Sustainability Governance** "[Governing Sustainability Transformations](#)" conference 15-17 October 2024.
2. Cluster meeting online **23 September 2024** (communications) and **04 October 2024**
3. Ongoing **sharing all our deliverables** via Zonodo.org

References

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- Nel, J. L., S. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, R. v. Dam, V. Ingram, and K. Korhonen-Kurki. 2023. Fishbowl dialogue on the opportunities and pitfalls of value-oriented transformative governance for biodiversity. 2023 Radboud Conference on Earth System Governance, , Nijmegen The Netherlands
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Appendix 1

11 projects funded under Horizon Europe Transformative change for Biodiversity:

BAMBOO

BIONEXT

BIOTraCeS

BIOTRAILS

BioValue

CLEVER

PLANET4B

RAINFOREST

SUSTAIN

TC4BE

TRANSPATH

This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.

Appendix 2

Links between Cluster projects in EU Horizon Biodiversity Call and other EU Horizon projects

Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
TRANSPATH - Transformative pathways for synergizing just biodiversity and climate actions	Francisco Alpizar	WUR	The global biodiversity and climate crises cannot be solved in isolation or by merely ramping up what is already being done. Urgent and ambitious transformative changes are needed in our economies and societies. Through inclusive deliberation TRANSPATH identifies leverage points and interventions for triggering transformative changes at consumer, producer and organisational levels. It seeks whole-of-society opportunities for achieving climate-neutrality whilst simultaneously allowing local communities and nature to flourish. TRANSPATH draws on diverse contexts in Eastern and Western Europe, Africa and Latin America, to engage with those who affect and are affected by trade regimes and associated 'greening' mechanisms. Through deliberation on alternative visions, values, actions, and their systemic interactions across scales and over time, TRANSPATH identifies leverage points that can trigger positive cascading biodiversity changes. Policy packages and other interventions are designed, to enable the emergence of leverage points at different scales of action in ways that changes the choice architecture underlying daily decisions. These interventions consider the synergies and trade-offs of actions across multiple people and places, and the role of incentives and political barriers to implementation. TRANSPATH delivers a suite of Transformative Pathways with a Toolbox of Transformative Interventions for triggering and enabling these pathways. A Transformative Navigation Toolkit guides practitioners on how to enable and navigate pathways, acknowledging that arriving at what constitutes a 'transformative pathway' is also a product of an iterative and	Cases 1-2: Eastern and Western Europe (WP2)	Coffee	Ghana			
	Jeanne Nel	WUR		Case 3: Global trade agreements and trade regulations (WP4)	Cocoa	Costa rica			
				Case 4: EU financial sector (WP4)		EU (Bulgaria)			
				Case 5: Teleconnected global value chain regulations and effects on land and forest protection/res toration (WP4)		Czech, Germany			
						Spain,			
				UK					
					Switzerland				

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Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
			adaptive process that emerges and evolves over time. To implement these, TRANSPATH develops a multi-scalar network of activated agents of change, who can foster inclusive and legitimate decisions, and build capacity and willingness among their actor networks to collectively move forward on transformative pathways.						
TC4BE - Transformative Change for biodiversity & Equity	Verina Ingram	WUR	co-generate knowledge, tools and stakeholder engagement on transformative change pathways of telecoupled agro-food systems to enhance biodiversity and equity outcomes	6 Cases: co-generated transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes in 6 Biodiversity rich innovation landscapes in 3 countries	(indirectly in landscapes) CAMEROON cocoa, NTFPs KENYA tea, horticulture COLOMBIA coffee, banana	Cameroon	Wageningen University (WU), NL Natural Resources Institute, University of Greenwich (UoG), UK Svenska Handelshögskolan, Finland Fondation Institut de Recherche pour le Développement Durable et des Relations Internationales (IDDRI), France Universidad de los Andes (UoA), Colombia Université de Dschang (UoD) Cameroon University of Kabianga (UoK) Kenya Centre de Coopération Internationale en Recherche Agronomique pour le	Social learning scenario development and modelling, cogenerate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative	SCP23: SCORAI-ERSCP-WUR Conference "Transforming consumption-production systems toward just and sustainable futures" (July 5-8, 2023, in Wageningen) contact@scp-conference-2023.com https://www.scp-conference-2023.com/web
	Valerie Nelson	NRI				Kenya			
	Thirza Hermans	WU				Colombia			
						EU (NL, France, Finland),			
						UK			

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Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
							Développement, France Global Landscapes Forum GLF		
CLEVER - Creating leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade	Jan Börner	Uni Bonn	Quantify impacts of the trade in raw and processed biomass on ecosystems, for offering new leverage points for biodiversity conservation, along supply chains, to reduce leakage effects modelling, economic methods, governance		Soy, pulp, timber, fishmeal, wood pulp	Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon, the EU	University of Bonn (UBO); 2. International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA); 3. University of Freiburg (UFR); 4. Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (UPV); 5. European Forest Institute (EFI); 6. Asociación BC3 Basque Centre For Climate Change - Klima Aldaketa Ikergai (BC3); 7. Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI); 8. University of Dschang (UDs); 9. Bonn.realis e.V. (Bonn.realis)	Econometrics, Simulation models measuring bio div, modelling biodiv, and policy views on governance of biodiversity. Not selected a landscape or area to work in - mission expected in sept 2023. leakage and psillover in VC- EFI.	
	mattias Cramm EFI								
	Yitagesu Tekle EFI								
	Yaghoob Jafari	Uni Bonn							
RAINFOREST - Coproduced transformative knowledge to accelerate change for biodiversity	Francesca Verones	NTNU Norway	Assessing the nexus of extraction, production, consumption, trade and behaviour patterns and of climate change action on biodiversity in the context of transformative change	telecoupling	Fishmeal	Peru			
					Plant forward food	Brazil			
					Plant based meal	EU			
						Norway			

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Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
						Germany			
						UK			

Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
<p>BIOTRAILS - Nexus framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change</p>	<p>Raffaele Giordano</p>	<p>ISR CNR Italy</p>	<p>BIOTRAILS aims to generate knowledge and develop tools that will inspire and accelerate biodiversity-relevant transformative change in our society. BIOTRAILS will use Participatory Systems Dynamics Modelling to take into account the complex interrelations between the indirect drivers of change in four value chains of traded products (cocoa produced in Peru; forest-based cultural products created by indigenous communities in the Brazilian Amazon; fisheries and aquaculture products supplied by the Mediterranean basin and consumed within the Mediterranean countries; and gold mined in Ghana), and in an integrated manner alongside the climate and social justice agendas. Based on this knowledge and tools, BIOTRAILS will bring together stakeholders across different stages of product/material global value chains to collaboratively design pathways that can lead to a sustainable future, proposing interventions in policy, urban consumption patterns and corporate policies. BIOTRAILS will set up Learning and Action Alliances: groups of organisations and individuals with a common interest to address the multiple challenges of climate change, biodiversity loss and people's good quality of life, across different spatial and administrative scales and stages of global value chains. Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output analysis and Life Cycle Assessment methods will be used to trace the environmental pressures arising from extraction / production, trade, and consumption activities, and behaviour patterns along global supply chains in the target sectors. The project will assess, besides the economic values, the biophysical, social and relational values emerging across different steps of value chain. Behavioural studies will be conducted based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour, which considers psychological and behavioural patterns. Structural Equation Models will be used to identify the most significant factors that drive behavioural change.</p>		<p>Cocoa fisheries & aquaculture products Gold</p>	<p>Peru Mediterranean Ghana</p>			

Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
FoSTA Health -	Stephen Whitfield	Leeds University	<p>Food Systems Transformation in Southern Africa for One Health (FoSTA-Health) will develop ambitious and inclusive visions of, and action plans for food systems transformation for achieving positive One Health outcomes in southern Africa. The project is centered around four key transformation agendas: (1) transformations within and out of maize; (2) transformations of land use and irrigation; (3) transformations from domestic to export markets; and (4) diet diversification. In relation to each, we will work with cross-system stakeholder groups (from government, industry, farmers, non-governmental organisations, and rural communities) and draw on evidence from case study contexts in Malawi, South Africa, Tanzania and Zambia to build an understanding of the complex system dynamics that link food systems transformation to diverse animal, environmental and human health outcomes. A set of representative transformation pathways (RTPs) describing alternative plausible transformation futures, will be outlined, and novel integrated modelling tools used to collaboratively evaluate the potential these offer for delivering positive One Health outcomes. This will be combined with a mapping and analysis of leverage points of food system transformation at local/landscape, national and regional government, and supply chain scales. Action plans will be developed and capacities built for supporting action around leverage points at each of these scales. Across FoSTA-Health particular attention will be paid to equity and justice in the visioning, governing and outcomes of transformative change. Critical reflection on participation and power dynamics within the focal contexts of the project, and within the project itself, will be the basis for making recommendations and advocating for the equitable and inclusive governance of food systems transformation.</p> <p>https://fanrpan.org/the-food-systems-transformation-in-southern-africa-for-one-health-fosta-health-project-launched/</p>	implications of different food system transformations in southern human, animal and environmental health. asking critical questions about equity, participation and plurality in visioning and governing transformation	Maize	Africa (specifically Malawi, Tanzania, South Africa and Zambia)	University of Leeds, WUR, FANRPAN, KULIMA South Africa, Southern African Business Development Forum, University of Zambia, Sokoine University of Agriculture, USTAV VYZKUMU GLOBALNI ZMENY, University of Pretoria, University of Nairobi CARE Austria,	formative accompanying research, critical self reflection on power and participation within the project itself (particularly in aspects of the project, participatory modelling).	
	Luuk Fleskens	WUR							

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Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
			https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060887						
BAMBOO - Biodiversity and trade: mitigating the impacts of non-food biomass global supply chains	Francesca Verones, Konstantin Stadler	Norges Tekniske Universitet Ntnu	Quantify impacts of the trade in raw and processed biomass on ecosystems, for offering new leverage points for biodiversity conservation, along supply chains, to reduce leakage effects WP1 : Quantify species diversity impacts WP2 : Quantify impacts on ecosystem functions WP3 : Impacts of trade in raw and processed non-food biomass hybrid (mixed-unit) MRIO model, WP4 : Assess leverage points for biodiversity conservation WP5 : Exploitation & Dissemination WP6 : Coordination & Management		Biomass	Global	ETH Zurich Min LNV NTNU University Leiden WU		
BIOVALUE - Biodiversity value in spatial policy and planning leveraging multi-level and transformative change	Maria Partidario Margarida Barata Monteiro	Uni Lisboa	Policy mixes, governance (including financing) and decision-making tools for transformative action on biodiversity						

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Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
						Country /areas			
BIONEXT - Biodiversity, water, food, energy, transport, climate and health nexus in the context of transformative change	Soile Ononen		BIONEXT will develop knowledge, tools, and guidance for mainstreaming biodiversity into policy making and provide concrete options on how to initiate, accelerate and upscale biodiversity relevant transformative change in society. It will deliver an innovative Nexus Modelling Framework that will integrate scenarios and pathways in a co-production process with stakeholders, while modelling interlinkages between biodiversity, water, food, energy, transport, climate, and health, and enabling simulation of the impacts of indirect and direct drivers on biodiversity. Through its database of transformative change cases, BIONEXT will involve policy- and decision-makers and allows them to explore the concept of just transformative change. Plausible futures and desirable, nature-positive visions for Europe and multiple just transition pathways will be co-created in workshops and focus groups taking place in various cities around Europe. With the involvement of diverse stakeholders, the BIONEXT Pathways App will be delivered as a novel decision support tool that allows users to explore transformational building blocks, for formulating policies and implementation pathways for the biodiversity nexus. The results will contribute to science brokerage, capacity building and networking to IPBES, EU policymakers, and civil society.						
BIOTraCes - Biodiversity and transformative change for plural and nature-positive societies			Understanding the role of behaviour, gender specifics, lifestyle, religious and cultural values, and addressing the role of enabling players (civil society, policy makers, financing and business leaders, retailers) in decision making						
PLANET4B -			Understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making						

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Project name	Coordinators	Lead org	Key aims	Cases	Commodities	Geographical focus	Project consortium partners	Methods	Key dates meetings etc
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SUSTAIN -			Strengthening Understanding and Strategies of business To Assess and Integrate Nature Impact and dependence of business on biodiversity						

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